

Performance Measurement of Popular Sorting Algorithm Implemented using Java & C++

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Abstract- Sorting and searching algorithms plays a vital role in almost all software products, hence efficiency of these algorithms should be of important concern. The rise of Java programming language two decades back had a great impact in design and development of software because of its features described in [11]. Java's capability of capturing the Internet programming made its roots more stronger. Hence making it a popular language for coding which has also kept back languages C++ and others. As per the theories Java's efficiency is mainly because of its Run Time execution of its Bytecode. Since Java has its foundation relying on C and C++ made us to take up this study to asymptotically analyze the popular sorting algorithm using C++ and Java, though it is seen sufficient analysis is done on sorting algorithms using C and C++ which correlated the theoretical analysis with practical measurements made through experiments. We conducted our research on two types of data sets, pseudo random numbers sets and sorted data sets. The results of experiments done on random data showed that n^2 class of sorting algorithms asymptotically performed faster in Java than C++ and $n \log n$ class of sorting algorithms performed better in C++ than with Java. The results of experiments on sorted data sets shows C++ performing very much better than Java, the poor performance of java for $n \log n$ class on both random and sorted data sets opens a study to be made on the design of 4GL compilers like Java, Python etc.

Keywords—sorting algorithms, asymptotic analysis, python, java, test bed, performance measurement,compiler design;

I. INTRODUCTION

In computer science, a sorting algorithm is an algorithm that puts elements of a list in a certain order. The most-used orders are numerical order and lexicographical order. Efficient sorting is important for optimizing the use of other algorithms (such as search and merge algorithms) that require sorted lists to work correctly; it is also often useful for canonicalizing data and for producing human-readable output.

More formally, the output must satisfy two conditions:

1. The output is in non-decreasing order
2. The output is a permutation, or reordering, of the input.

Since the dawn of computing, the sorting problem has attracted a great deal of research, perhaps due to the complexity of solving it efficiently despite its simple, familiar statement. For example, bubble sort was analyzed as early as 1956. later other algorithms like selection sort, insertion sort merge sort, quick sort and many others methods were introduced which we term as popular sorting algorithms. Due to fast evolution in computer technology, although many consider it a solved problem, useful new sorting algorithms are still being invented. The evolution in technologies like Data sciences, Data Analytics , Machine learning etc also gives the researchers an opportunity to come up with still better results and solutions.

II. ASYMPTOTIC ANALYSIS

The word asymptotic means that it is the study of function of a parameter n , as n become larger and larger without any bounds. Here we are concerned with how the runtime of an algorithm increases with the size of the input. We can do analysis of algorithms which will accurately reflect the way in which the computation time will increase with the size, but ignores the other details with little effect on total. It permits us to provide upper and lower bounds on the value of a function f for suitably large values. The efficiency analysis frame work concentrates on order of growth of an algorithms' basic operation count as the principal indicator of the algorithms' efficiency. To compare and rank such orders of growth, computer scientist use three notations:

- $O(\text{big-oh})$
- $\Omega(\text{big-omega})$
- $\Theta(\text{big-theta})$

$O(\text{big-oh})$ bounds from above , Ω (big-omega) from bottom and $\Theta(\text{big-theta})$ does from both above and below, details study is given in [1][2].

In the following section we have briefly explained the theoretical aspects of the popular sorting algorithm namely merge sort, quick sort and others like Bubble,selection and Insertion sort. .

III. SORTING ALGORITHMS

A. MERGE SORT

The merge sort splits the list to be sorted into two equal halves, and places them in separate arrays. This sorting method is an example of the DIVIDE-AND-CONQUER paradigm i.e. it breaks the data into two halves and then sorts the two half data sets recursively, and finally merges them to obtain the complete sorted list. The merge sort is a comparison sort and has an algorithmic complexity of $O(n \log n)$. Elementary implementations of the merge sort make use of two arrays - one for each half of the data set. The following image depicts the complete procedure of merge sort.

Pros: 1) marginally faster than the heap sort for larger sets. 2) Merge Sort always does lesser number of comparisons than Quick Sort. Worst case for merge sort does about 39% less comparisons against quick sort's average case. 3) Merge sort is often the best choice for sorting a linked list because the slow random-access performance of a linked list makes some other algorithms (such as quick sort) perform poorly, and others (such as heap sort) completely impossible.

Cons: 1) At least twice the memory requirements of the other sorts because it is recursive. This is the BIGGEST cause for concern as its space complexity is very high. It requires about a $\Theta(n)$ auxiliary space for its working. 2) Function overhead calls ($2n-1$) are much more than those for quick sort (n). This causes it to take more time marginally to sort the input data.

B. QUICK SORT

Quick Sort is an algorithm based on the DIVIDE-AND-CONQUER paradigm that selects a pivot element and reorders the given list in such a way that all elements smaller to it are on one side and those bigger than it are on the other. Then the sub lists are recursively sorted until the list gets completely sorted. The time complexity of this algorithm is $O(n \log n)$.

Pros: 1) One advantage of parallel quick sort over other parallel sort algorithms is that no synchronization is required. A new thread is started as soon as a sub list is available for it to work on and it does not communicate with other threads. When all threads complete, the sort is done. 2) All comparisons are being done with a single pivot value, which can be stored in a register. 3) The list is being traversed sequentially, which produces very good locality of reference and cache behavior for arrays.

Cons: 1) Auxiliary space used in the average case for implementing recursive function calls is $O(\log n)$ and hence proves to be a bit space costly, especially when it comes to large data sets. 2) Its worst case has a time complexity of $O(n^2)$ which can prove very fatal for large data sets. Competitive sorting algorithms

C. INSERTION SORT, SELECTION SORT AND BUBBLE SORT

These are classified as n^2 class of sorting algorithms, these very slow than the $n \log n$ class discussed in the above section.

Insertion sort collects and places the first element in the first index of empty array and subsequent elements are placed by comparing it with the elements from one side and after insertion in its place the algorithm shifts the elements of other side, this is repeated for every new insertion.

Bubble sort does the sorting by comparing n elements and swaps the the unsorted into the order, this process is repeated for similar n passes.

Selection sort, which also does the sorting in n passes, at every pass it picks the min number and puts it in its order. In selection sort few comparison are avoided in comparison to bubble sort making it little better.

These basic algorithms, the Bubble sort or Selection sort are inefficient in nature but very easy to code. They are of importance in academic studies but are not in concern at practices. On the other side Insertion sort though being in the class of order n^2 performs well to sort small sample sizes along with $n \log n$ class algorithms. Insertion sort is faster among the n^2 class of sorting algorithms. As our intention of this paper is to make analysis and performance measurement of sorting algorithms implemented using the most popular programming languages Java and Python. The performance measurement and observations are only possible by considering asymptotic analysis which is explained briefly in the next section.

IV. RELATED WORK

Sufficient work on asymptotic analysis and performance measurement of the above popular sorting algorithms have been done in [1][4]. Also my paper [8] has made asymptotic analysis and performance measurement of popular sorting algorithms by implementing them in C language and has exhibited the true behaviors of the popular sorting algorithms. The paper [8] also shows the **Asymptotic Point(AP)** or the time taken for that sample from which onwards the sorting algorithm enter into the **Asymptotic Behavior Range (ABR)**, here Range refers to data samples or set greater than that sample size by which we achieved the AP. Further, when we found the popularity of java over taking very fast its predecessors like C++ though it has foundation of C and C++ in its virtual machine. Therefore, in order to find how well Java perform for popular sorting algorithms in contrast with C++ and to observe their performance and behaviors we took up this research.

V. PERFORMANCE MEASUREMENT

A. EXPERIMENT SET-UP

Performance measurement is concerned with obtaining the actual time requirements of a program. To obtain the execution time of a program in C++, we need a clocking mechanism. We have used the `clock()` which returns the number of clock ticks elapsed since the program got executed. We need to include the Header File "time.h" and declare `clock_t clock(void)`; which returns a value : On success, the

value returned is the CPU time used so far as a clock_t; To get the number of seconds used, divide by CLOCKS_PER_SEC on error -1 is returned. Similarly in Java system class in library has methods like nanoTime() and currentTimeMillis() which returns time in Nano and Milli seconds respectively.

As we expect the asymptotic behavior to begin for larger values of n as it is shown in [8]. For safer to exhibit Asymptotic behaviors of sorting algorithms we have our sample size range n=1000,2000,.. ,10000, 20000,. .100000. . 500000. We have considered two class of data samples as mentioned in above section for conducting our experiment to testify the average and the worst case of algorithms. First, random samples for average case analysis which we generated by using random numbers generator methods in both C++ and java languages by importing their respective classes given below:

In C++, rand() function is an inbuilt function in C++ STL, which is defined in header file <cstdlib>. rand() is used to generate a series of random numbers. The srand() function sets the starting point for producing a series of pseudo-random integers

In Java, Import java.util.Random; and the method Random() called through its object, ie., Random generator = new random().

Second, samples for worst case analysis for this the array index is assigned as the array element, a[i]=n-i-1(descending order. For simplicity purpose best case analysis we neglect it as it has less importance in sorting.

The two driver codes, which initiates the experiment execution for both C++ and Java respectively are given below:

Driver code of C++

```
int main ()
{
int max=500000;
int data[max];
float x,y;
clock_t time_req;
int step=100000;
for(int n=500000;n<=max;n=n+step){
//if (n==100000)step=100000;
srand((unsigned) time(0));
for (int i=0;i<n; i++)
data[i]= n-i-1; // for descending order data set
//data[i]=rand(); // for random data set
time_req = clock();
//bubbleSort(data,n);
selectionSort(data,n);
//insertionSort(data,n);
//mergeSort(data,0,n-1);
//quickSort(data,0,n-1);
//iterativeQuicksort(data, n);
```

```
time_req = clock() - time_req;
cout << (float)time_req/CLOCKS_PER_SEC << endl;
}
return 0;
}
//time_req is the time taken by the algorithm to sort the
//sample
// Driver code of Java program (calling selection sort)
public static void main(String[] args){
int[] a;
int i,step=1000;
for(int n=1000;n<=max;n=n+step){
if (n >= 10000) step=10000;
a = new int[max];
Random generator = new Random();
for(i=0;i<n;i++)
a[i]=generator.nextInt(100));
long startTime = System.nanoTime();
SelectionSort ss = new SelectionSort();
ss.selectionSort(a);
long stopTime = System.nanoTime();
long elapsedTime = (stopTime - startTime);
System.out.println("Time taken to Sort n elements
="+n + " is :"+elapsedTime + " nanoseconds\n");
} //sample loop
} // main body end
```

Note: we enable each call of sorting method by removing the '//' (comment symbol) and disabling the others by adding '// ' symbol for the other sorting methods calls in case of python. Similarly we do it in case of java . The sample sizes are obtained by using for loop with suitable step size in C++ and Java to form the range of data and random method used in both C++ and java to generate pseudo random numbers.

The system configuration of the test bed is specified below.

Test bed : Memory of 3.7 GiB, Intel® Core™ i3-6006U CPU @ 2.00GHz × 4 ,64-bit, 970.9 GB

As mentioned earlier we have used two types of data set, the random data set and ordered data set (for worst case analysis, generation of these data is mentioned above) over which we conduct our experiments.

B. EXPERIMENT RESULTS AND OBSERVATIONS

We have conducted **two different class of experiments**, in the first one we conducted experiments on different samples of pseudo random numbers using both C++ and Java languages and the second one conducting experiments on different samples of decreasing order numbers using both C++ and Java languages. Following paragraphs illustrates the observations made from the two perspective, of implementations with respect to two different programming

languages java and C++ for two class of data (random data and decreasing order data) .

i. EXPERIMENTING WITH RANDOM DATA SET

Table 1 and Table 2 along with their respective graph plots in Figure 1 and Figure 2 shows the results of experiments done on Pseudo random numbers using C++ and Java languages. By making observation from Table 1 and Table 2, and their respective Graphs shows clearly that sorting algorithms Quick sort, Merge sort, Insertion sort, Bubble sort and Selection sort have performed as per their asymptotic behavior and order of growths as explained in [1][2][3]. Quick sort and Merge sort being the fast as it belong to the $n \log n$ class among the order of growth classes as listed in [2]. Insertion sort, selection sort and bubble sort are slow in execution since they belong to quadratic (n^2) class among the order of growth classes. Further it is seen that Quick sort and Merge sort has performed slow in its Java implementations and are more faster in the C++ implementation. The reasons of being slow in Java implementation can be due to compiler design for Java language which could be the reason that it's JVM is written using C and C++.

In Table 1 for random data sample we observe Asymptotic time taken with C++ for sample size 10000 (first row) for Quick sort is 0.010271 seconds where as time taken for the same sample size for Merge sort is 0.00292 indicating that merge sort is fastest with C++ Implementation than Quick sort initially and later for sample size 100000 and 400000 we observe Quick sort becomes faster than Merge sort in its ABR. The other sorting algorithms behaves as per their behaviors discussed in the theories given in [1][2] and also realised the same in [8].

In Table 2, for random data sample we observe Asymptotic time taken with Java code for sample size 10000 for Quick sort is 0.008 faster than its C++ implementation but later we find the time is 1.881 seconds slower than its C++ implementation which is 0.118071 seconds. Further we observe that the time taken for Merge sort in its Java implementation is 69.616 for sample size 400000 and time taken in its C++ implementation is 0.1395 making Merge sort too slow in Java Implementation. Also we notice that Bubble sort, Selection sort and Insertion sort perform well in its ABR in Java implementation when compare to their C++ implementation. The reason of this could be less overheads in their algorithm which works well with java implementation. The same is in opposite in case of $n \log n$ class i.e., Quick sort and merge sort. Since n^2 class algorithms have no practical applicability in software systems the speed may not be of

consideration. Where as $n \log n$ class of sorting algorithms perform well in C++.

TABLE 1
ASYMPTOTIC TIME TAKEN ON TEST BED USING C++ CODE FOR RANDOM DATA SAMPLES

Sample size	Bubble sort Time in sec	Selection sort Time in sec	Insertion Sort Time in sec	Merge sort Time in sec	Quick Sort Time taken
10000	0.402615	0.17962	0.109579	0.002922	0.010271
20000	1.77863	0.719717	0.434557	0.0057	0.01926
30000	4.10188	1.68225	0.971667	0.008918	0.013325
40000	7.43798	2.89585	1.71888	0.011887	0.011883
50000	11.8442	4.49374	2.70013	0.01557	0.012839
60000	17.1292	6.46548	4.0114	0.0182	0.015463
70000	23.5858	8.86003	5.36234	0.022042	0.019609
80000	31.2083	12.4205	6.86718	0.025388	0.021295
90000	39.3734	15.28	8.85953	0.028719	0.024223
100000	48.755	18.2481	10.8795	0.031991	0.027073
200000	204.018	84.8423	45.7313	0.070883	0.067786
300000	458.99	191.594	104.348	0.102785	0.08744
400000	828.417	341.353	185.874	0.139571	0.118071

FIG 1: GRAPH PLOT FOR TABLE 1 VALUES, X-AXIS REPRESENTS SAMPLE SIZE AND Y-AXIS SHOWS THE TIME TAKEN IN SECONDS

TABLE 2
ASYMPTOTIC TIME TAKEN ON TEST BED USING JAVA CODE FOR RANDOM DATA SAMPLES

Sample size	Quick Sort Time in sec	Merge sort Time in sec	Insertion Sort Time in sec	Selection sort Time in sec	Bubble sort Time in sec
10000	0.008	1.968	0.033	0.120	0.273
20000	0.007	3.411	0.089	0.428	1.199
30000	0.013	5.029	0.209	6.47	2.364
40000	0.019	6.789	0.355	1.124	5.216
50000	0.029	8.425	0.556	1.859	6.572
60000	0.045	10.032	0.831	2.548	9.482
70000	0.061	11.817	1.133	3.511	12.800
80000	0.079	13.584	1.806	4.621	16.842
90000	0.100	15.080	1.829	5.985	21.250
100000	0.1122	17.651	2.297	7.299	26.347
200000	0.471	35.600	9.221	32.103	110.425
300000	1.075	52.400	20.789	65.924	241.174
400000	1.881	69.616	37.971	115.139	427.947

Fig 2 GRAPH PLOT FOR TABLE 4 VALUES, X-AXIS REPRESENTS SAMPLE SIZE AND Y-AXIS SHOWS THE TIME TAKEN IN SECONDS

ii. EXPERIMENTING WITH SORTED DATA SET

As mentioned in the experiment set-up section, we have mentioned how to generate sorted data set. Sorted data set is considered for analyzing the worst case behaviors especially for the $n \log n$ class of sorting algorithms which are very much faster than algorithms belonging to n^2 class i.e., Quick sort and Merge sort in case of random data samples. Table 3 and Table 4 along with their graph plots in Figure 3 and Figure 4 respectively shows the results of experiments done on sorted numbers using C++ and Java languages The time clocked nano and millis later converted to second(sec).

In case of C++ implementation of Mergesort for $n=500000$ on sorted data set its clocks the time 0.099834 seconds where as Quick sort as known by its Worst case complexity $O(n^2)$ takes 809.665 seconds which resembles that of the n^2 class algorithms, time taken for the same sample size for Bubble sort is 827.23 seconds for selection sort it is 483.659 seconds and for Insertion sort it is 537.935 seconds. As average case for merge sort as given in [1][2] it is $\Theta(n \log n)$ and hence it perform very near in speed in its implementation in C++ for both type of data (random and sorted) but it is seen that the performance in its java implementations it is not normal as per the theories given in [1][2]. This is also in the case of Quick sort, Insertion sort and selection sort. We also observe that time taken to sort the sorted data using Quick sort takes a time 1812.31 seconds for sample size is 500000 which does not proportionates with the algorithms of n^2 class, which we find it in case of C++ implementation which adheres to the theoretical analysis made by experts given in[1][2]. This peculiar issue which gives rise to a research study regarding design of 4GL compilers like Java and Python.

TABLE 3
ASYMPTOTIC TIME TAKEN ON TEST BED FOR C++ CODE ON SORTED DATA SAMPLES

Sample size	Bubble sort Time in sec	Selection sort Time in sec	Insertion Sort Time in sec	Merge sort Time in sec	Quick Sort Time taken
10000	0.348765	0.188348	0.217146	0.001947	0.327025
20000	1.31706	0.75181	0.861631	0.003275	1.30349
30000	2.98455	1.69115	1.94164	0.005278	2.92996
40000	5.29415	3.0071	3.44723	0.006751	5.20315
50000	8.52272	4.76164	5.42916	0.010155	8.13089
60000	11.9832	6.94479	7.74651	0.010365	11.7192
70000	16.2143	9.37635	10.539	0.012186	15.9394
80000	23.6834	12.4428	13.7893	0.015152	20.8201
90000	28.5272	15.5903	17.3839	0.015903	26.4484
100000	33.6542	19.1	21.479	0.01901	32.6818
200000	133.496	77.4486	86.1923	0.039253	134.072
300000	299.489	174.771	193.365	0.058425	295.033
400000	530.479	301.901	344.659	0.079388	529.134
500000	827.23	483.659	537.935	0.099834	809.665

Fig 3 GRAPH PLOT FOR TABLE 5 VALUES, X-AXIS REPRESENTS SAMPLE SIZE AND Y-AXIS SHOWS THE TIME TAKEN IN SECONDS

TABLE 4
ASYMPTOTIC TIME TAKEN ON TEST BED FOR JAVA CODE ON SORTED DATA SAMPLES

Sample Size	Quick sort Time in sec	Merge sort Time in sec	Insertion sort Time in sec	Selection sort Time in sec	Bubble sort Time in sec
10000	0.87	25.25	0.54	0.32	0.47
20000	3.09	33.48	1.84	0.92	1.56
30000	7.07	51.26	3.98	2.37	2.93
40000	12.54	67.51	7.14	3.67	6.19
50000	16.26	84.46	11.24	5.70	9.49
60000	25.56	102.03	16.02	8.25	13.85
70000	34.56	119.61	21.99	10.96	18.87
80000	45.05	137.71	28.88	14.88	24.54
90000	57.04	153.69	36.37	18.40	31.16
100000	70.44	169.90	44.90	25.86	32.58
200000	283.43	337.16	181.17	104.96	131.53
300000	650.18	530.29	415.99	236.41	295.66
400000	1142.17	696.76	749.28	429.95	529.66
500000	1812.31	875.73	1167.27	670.42	848.90

FIG 4: GRAPH PLOT FOR TABLE 6 VALUES, X-AXIS REPRESENTS SAMPLE SIZE AND Y-AXIS SHOWS THE TIME TAKEN IN SECONDS

VI. CONCLUSION

The results of experiments done on random data showed that **n^2 class** of sorting algorithms asymptotically performed faster in Java than C++ and **$n \log n$ class** of sorting algorithms performed better in C++ than with its Java implementation. The results of experiments on sorted data sets shows C++ performing very much better than Java, the poor performance of java for $n \log n$ class on both random and sorted data sets opens a study to be made on the design of 4GL compilers like Java, Python etc. As per our studies made middle level languages like C and C++ are more suitable when time efficiency is preferred other wise languages like Java and Python can be opted. The study also suggest the theoreticians to keep an birds eye when data structures and algorithms being implemented from the diverse set of programming languages. Also theoreticians can lay down some criteria in selecting a programming language for solving problems or for developing a software application.

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